

Spin and the Orthogonality of Spatial Axes?

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In a previous note (1), we argued that the mathematical probability $\exp(ipx)$ ensures conservation of momentum, but only through the introduction of an extra variable, x , and orthogonality in space. The conserved quantity p is also associated with motion in x . At the same time, p is linked to the usual Newtonian ideas of kinetic energy, i.e. $pp/2m$ at any x (nonrelativistic) and $EE=pp+momo$ ($c=1$), relativistic. Energy considerations are important for the $\exp(ipx)$ form because $\exp(ipx)$ is not only a probability which ensures momentum conservation, but it is a solution of both $EE= pp+momo$ and $E=pp/2m$ with p replaced with $-i d/dx$. Furthermore, the time-independent Schrodinger equation is based on average energy conservation: $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx + V(x)=En$, where $W= \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

We suggest here that if the orthogonality of $\exp(ipx)$ for different p values in x is indicative of a conserved quantity, p , associated with motion in x , then one should also take note of the orthogonality in the co-ordinate axes which give rise to $pp = p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$. Such an orthogonality could be associated with motion linked to moving one axis into another, i.e. rotation, i.e. there would exist a kind of conserved angular momentum associated with co-ordinate orthogonality. In Newtonian physics, such considerations do not occur.

$\exp(ipx)$ and Conservation of Momentum

In (1), we suggested that one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ by taking classical Newtonian conservation of momentum and asking: What probability function ensures this conservation? First of all, $P(p_1)P(p_2) = P(p_1+p_2)$. For momentum conservation, we suggested using a minus sign for a result after a collision, i.e.

$P(-p_3)P(-p_4)P(p_1)P(p_2)$ should be 0 unless $p_1+p_2 = p_3+p_4$ (one dimension) ((1))

If one only uses p values, it does not seem possible to obtain ((1)), but if a second variable, x , is introduced, then for $P(p)=\exp(ipx)$ one has the required condition ((1)) if one integrates over x . We also note that p must have motion in x even though $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ etc (nonrelativistically) and a similar relativistic condition.

Thus, orthogonality in space is associated with a conserved motion variable, p , where the motion is in x . As a result, we suggest that orthogonality becomes an important physical concept.

Energy Considerations

In the above paragraph, we suggested that $\exp(ipx)$ is the probability which ensures momentum conservation. This implies that there is a wavelength region, \hbar/p , with different probability values for different x , but p and $pp/2m$ (nonrelativistic) or $EE=pp+momo$ ($c=1$) still

holds for any x . In other words, energy considerations do not disappear. Furthermore, $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution of:

$$E = \frac{p^2}{2m} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d^2 W}{dx^2} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2)) \quad \text{for } p = -i \hbar \frac{d}{dx}$$

If one has a potential $V(x)$, then one may create $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and use average energy conservation (i.e. the time-independent Schrodinger equation):

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \hbar^2 \frac{d^2 W}{dx^2} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((3))$$

As a result, classical energy conservation equations such as: $KE(x)+V(x)= E_n$ or $E = \frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x)$ may be applied to the $\exp(ipx)$ picture, but $p \rightarrow -i \hbar \frac{d}{dx}$.

If this is the case, we argue that one must view orthogonality which occurs in energy expressions in the same manner. In particular, we suggest focusing on $p \cdot p$.

Orthogonality Linked to Space as a Signature of a Conserved Quantity Linked to Motion in Space?

We already noted that orthogonality in x of $\exp(ipx)$ with $\exp(-ip_2 x)$ is associated with momentum conservation in x , where there is motion in x . In the case of:

$$p \cdot p = p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z \quad ((4))$$

we suggest that there exists orthogonality between the x,y,z basis vectors. In classical physics, this is not associated with a conserved quantity, but to be consistent with $\exp(ipx)$, we suggest that it should. If one tries to move one basis vector into another, i.e. rotate it, this would be associated with a kind of angular motion or momentum. Thus, orthogonality of coordinates may be linked with a conserved angular type of momentum even for a particle with a constant p moving in one direction. Such an idea does not appear in classical physics and seems like a paradox, but the Stern-Gerlach experimental results show that electrons have two different states linked to interactions with a magnetic field.

Dirac Equation

We have suggested above that orthogonality of spatial basis vectors in $p \cdot p$ imply a conserved angular momentum type object, but how is this quantified? In the case of $\exp(ipx)$, one replaces p with $-i \hbar \frac{d}{dx}$ in energy equations. As a result, one may try to introduce operators, i.e. Pauli spin matrices, which account for the orthogonality in the co-ordinates. This approach was already introduced by Dirac who linearized $E = \frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x)$ ((5)) ($c=1$). This equation contains $p^2 = p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$ which already contains the co-ordinate orthogonality, so one wishes to split the equation into two pieces, like $\int dx \exp(-ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x)$, to see orthogonality emerge. This leads to a linear operator equation which when multiplied by its conjugate yields ((5)) The only way to create such a linear operator is to introduce matrices

(4x4) which contain the Pauli spin matrices which ultimately ensure orthogonality of co-ordinate basis vectors.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argued that momentum conservation is imposed by hand in Newtonian mechanics, e.g. in the scattering of two particles. If one wishes to create a probability function such that: $P(p_3, p_4 \text{ final} | p_1, p_2 \text{ initial}) = 0$ if $p_1 + p_2 \neq p_3 + p_4$, otherwise 1, then $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution, but one must integrate over x . In other words, orthogonality in x is required in order to have a conserved momentum linked to motion in x .

We further argued that energy conservation equations from classical physics may be used with this $\exp(ipx)$ probability picture if $p \rightarrow -i \hbar d/dx$.

We next suggested that the orthogonality of $p \cdot p = p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$ in both relativistic and nonrelativistic energy equations may also imply the conservation of a momentum linked with rotating one co-ordinate basis vector into another. This seems like a paradox if p is constant, unless there is an internal angular momentum in the particle.

In order to quantitatively see this conserved quantity, one may consider $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$ (with $c=1$) with $p = -i \hbar d/dx$ and try to break it into two operator pieces. In such a case a matrix operator ensures the orthogonality of basis vectors. One does not have to integrate over any variable. Dirac already performed this calculation to demonstrate spin in an electron. His 4x4 matrices are linked to Pauli's 2x2 matrices which ensure orthogonality of co-ordinate basis vectors.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Conservation of Momentum in Terms of Probability, Space, Time (preprint, zenodo, 2024)